

Some Fundamental Properties of Hunaiber Transform and its Applications to Partial Differential Equations

Mona Hunaiber¹, Ali Al-Aati²

^{1,2} Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Education and Sciences, Albaydha University, Yemen.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 20 July 2022	In this paper, we study some basic properties of a new integral transform " Hunaiber transform". Moreover, we apply Hunaiber transform to solve linear partial differential equations with initial and boundary conditions. We solve first order partial differential equations and Second order partial differential equations which are essential equations in mathematical physics and applied mathematics.
Corresponding Author: Mona Hunaiber, Ali Al-Aati	
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I. INTRODUCTION

The source of the integral transforms can be traced back to the work of P. S. Laplace in 1780s and Joseph Fourier in 1822. In recent years, integral and differential equations have been solved using many integral trans-forms. The integral transformation method is extremely used to solve different kinds of differential equations in a simple way. As integral transforms converts differential equations into algebraic equations which are more simple than differential equations. Many problems of physical interest are described by integral and differential equa-tions with appropriate or boundary conditions. These problems are usually formulated as initial value problem, boundary value problems, or initial-boundary value pro-blem that appear to be mathematically more vigorous and physically realistic in engineering sciences and applied. There are numerous integral transforms and all of them are suitable to resolve various types' differential equa-tions. Many researchers have turned their attention to solve partial differential equation and to develop new methods for solving such equations. The behavior of the solutions very much depend fundamentally on the classification of partial differential equations, then the problem of classification for partial differential equations well known since the classification controls the adequate number and the type of the conditions in order to determine whether the problem is well posed and has a unique solution. Many researchers developed lot of integral transforms like Laplace, Kamal,

Fourier, Elzaki, Sawi, Aboodh, Mahgoub, Shehu, etc. transforms.

Mona Hunaiber introduce new integral transform called as Hunaiber transform.

The Hunaiber transform is a new integral transform similar to the Laplace transform and other integral tran-sforms.

1. 1 Definition.

Let $f(x)$ be piecewise continuous on the interval $0 \leq x \leq \lambda$ for any $\lambda > 0$, and $|f(x)| \leq Me^{ax}$ where $x \geq N$, for any real constant a and some positive constants M and N . The Hunaiber transform is defined by

$$H[f(x)] = F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) = \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f(x) dx, \quad (1)$$

Where μ complex is variable, β is real number and α is any nonzero real number. Here H is called the Hunaiber transform operator.

It turns out that the Hunaiber transform has very special and useful properties to simplify the process of solving differential equations.

II. SOME PROPERTIES OF HUNAIBER TRANSFORM

(1). Linearity Property

If Hunaiber transform of functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ are $F_1(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$ and $F_2(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$ respectively, then Hunaiber transform of $a f_1(x) + b f_2(x)$ is given by

$$a F_1(\mu^\alpha, \beta) + b F_2(\mu^\alpha, \beta), \tag{2}$$

where a and b are arbitrary constants.

Proof. By definition of Hunaiber transform, we have $H[a f_1(x) + b f_2(x)]$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} (a f_1(x) + b f_2(x)) dx \\ &= a \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f_1(x) dx + b \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f_2(x) dx \\ &= a F_1(\mu^\alpha, \beta) + b F_2(\mu^\alpha, \beta). \end{aligned}$$

(2). Shifting property If Hunaiber transform of function $f(x)$ is $F(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$, then for any real constant $a > 0$, we have

$$H[e^{ax} f(x)] = F(\mu^\alpha - a, \beta). \tag{3}$$

Proof. Using the definition of Hunaiber transform, we have

$$\begin{aligned} H[e^{ax} f(x)] &= \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} e^{ax} f(x) dx \\ &= \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-(\mu^\alpha - a)x} f(x) dx \\ &= F(\mu^\alpha - a, \beta). \end{aligned}$$

(3). Change of scale Property

If Hunaiber transform of function $f(x)$ is $F(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$, then Hunaiber transform of function $f(ax)$ is given by $\frac{1}{a} F\left(\frac{\mu^\alpha}{a}, \beta\right)$, where a is positive constant.

Proof. Using the definition of Hunaiber transform, we have

$$H[f(ax)] = \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f(ax) dx.$$

Set $r = ax$, then

$$\begin{aligned} H[f(ax)] &= \frac{\mu^\beta}{a} \int_0^\infty e^{-\left(\frac{\mu^\alpha}{a}\right)r} f(r) dr \\ &= \frac{1}{a} F\left(\frac{\mu^\alpha}{a}, \beta\right). \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

(4). Hunaiber Transform of the function $xf(x)$

Let $F(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$ be the Hunaiber transform of function $f(x)$, then

$$H[xf(x)] = \frac{-1}{\alpha \mu^{\alpha-1}} \left[\frac{d}{d\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) - \frac{\beta}{\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) \right]. \tag{5}$$

Proof. Since $H[f(x)] = F(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) &= \frac{d}{d\mu} \left[\mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f(x) dx \right] \\ \frac{d}{d\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) &= -\alpha \mu^{\alpha-1} \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} x f(x) dx \\ &\quad + \beta \mu^{\beta-1} \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d}{d\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) = -\alpha \mu^{\alpha-1} H[xf(x)] + \frac{\beta}{\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta)$$

Hence, we obtain

$$H[xf(x)] = \frac{-1}{\alpha \mu^{\alpha-1}} \left[\frac{d}{d\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) - \frac{\beta}{\mu} F(\mu^\alpha, \beta) \right].$$

2.1 Theorem: If $F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta)$ is a Hunaiber transform of $f(x, y)$ and $f_x(x, y)$ is a first partial derivative of $f(x, y)$ with respect to variable x , then

$$H[f_x(x, y)] = F_x(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) \tag{6}$$

Also, we have

$$H[f_{xx}(x, y)] = F_{xx}(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) \tag{7}$$

$$H[f_{x^n}(x, y)] = F_{x^n}(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) \tag{8}$$

2.2 Theorem: If $F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta)$ is a Hunaiber transform of $f(x, y)$ and $f_y(x, y)$ is a first partial derivative of $f(x, y)$ with respect to variable y , then

$$H[f_y(x, y)] = \mu^\alpha F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^\beta f(x, 0). \tag{9}$$

Proof. Using the definition(1), we have

$$H[f_y(x, y)] = \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f_y(x, y) dy$$

By using integration by part, we obtain

$$H[f_y(x, y)] = \mu^\alpha F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^\beta f(x, 0).$$

2.3 Theorem: If $F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta)$ is a Hunaiber transform of $f(x, y)$ and $f_{yy}(x, y)$ is a second partial derivative of $f(x, y)$ with respect to variable y , then

$$\begin{aligned} H[f_{yy}(x, y)] &= \mu^{2\alpha} F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^{\alpha+\beta} f(x, 0) \\ &\quad - \mu^\beta f_y(x, 0) \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Proof. Using the definition(1), we have

$$H[f_{yy}(x, y)] = \mu^\beta \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f_{yy}(x, y) dy$$

By using integration by part, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} H[f_{yy}(x, y)] &= -\mu^\beta f_y(x, 0) + \mu^\alpha \mu^\beta \left\{ -f(x, 0) + \mu^\alpha \int_0^\infty e^{-x\mu^\alpha} f(x, y) dy \right\} \\ H[f_{yy}(x, y)] &= \mu^{2\alpha} F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^{\alpha+\beta} f(x, 0) - \mu^\beta f_y(x, 0). \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

III. APPLICATIONS

In this section, we assume that the inverse Hunaiber transform exists. We apply the inverse Hunaiber transform to find the solution of linear partial differential equations with initial and boundary conditions. We solve first order partial differential equations and the Second order partial differential equations, Laplace, wave, heat equations which are known as three Fundamental equations in mathematical physics and arise in many branches of physics in applied mathematics.

Example3.1. Consider the first order partial differential equation

$$f_x(x, y) - 2f_y(x, y) = f(x, y), \tag{12}$$

With initial condition

$$f(x, 0) = e^{-3x} \tag{13}$$

Take Hunaiber transform to this equation, we gives

$$F_x(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - 2[\mu^\alpha F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^\beta f(x, 0)] = F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta),$$

Where $F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta)$ is Hunaiber transform of $f(x, y)$. by applied initial condition, we get

$$F_x(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - (2\mu^\alpha + 1)F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = -2\mu^\beta e^{-3x}$$

This is linear ordinary differential equation, it has the integration factor $e^{-(2\mu^\alpha+1)x}$. Hence

$$F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = e^{-3x} \frac{\mu^\beta}{\mu^\alpha + 2}$$

Now, applying the inverse Hunaiber transform of last equation, then the solution of Eq. (12) is

$$f(x, y) = e^{-(3x+2y)}.$$

Example 3.2 Consider the Laplace equation

$$f_{xx}(x, y) + f_{yy}(x, y) = 0, \quad (14)$$

With conditions

$$f(x, 0) = 0, \quad f_y(x, 0) = \cos x. \quad (15)$$

Take Hunaiber transform to this equation gives

$$F_{xx}(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) + \mu^{2\alpha}F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^{\alpha+\beta} f(x, 0) - \mu^\beta f_y(x, 0) = 0$$

By applied the conditions (15), we get

$$F_{xx}(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) + \mu^{2\alpha}F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = \mu^\beta \cos x$$

It is second order ordinary differential equation, thus its particular solution is

$$F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\mu^\beta}{\mu^{2\alpha} - 1} \cos x$$

Taking inverse Hunaiber transform, we get

$$f(x, y) = \cos x \sinh y.$$

Example 3.3 Consider the wave equation

$$f_{tt}(x, t) - 4 f_{xx}(x, t) = 0, \quad x, t > 0. \quad (16)$$

With conditions

$$f(x, 0) = \sin \pi x, \quad f_t(x, 0) = 0. \quad (17)$$

Take Hunaiber transform to Eq. (16), and use the conditions (17), we get

$$F_{xx}(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \frac{\mu^{2\alpha}}{4} F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = -\frac{\mu^{\alpha+\beta}}{4} \sin \pi x$$

This is the second order differential equation have the particular solution in the form

$$F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\mu^{\alpha+\beta} \sin \pi x}{\mu^{2\alpha} + 4\pi^2}$$

Taking inverse Hunaiber transform, we get

$$f(x, t) = \sin \pi x \cos 2\pi t.$$

Example 3.4 Consider the heat equation

$$f_t(x, t) = f_{xx}(x, t), \quad (18)$$

With conditions

$$f(0, t) = 0, \quad f(x, 0) = 3 \sin 2\pi t. \quad (19)$$

Applying the Hunaiber transform on both sides of Eq. (18), And substituting the given conditions, we get

$$F_{xx}(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) - \mu^\alpha F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = -3\mu^\beta \sin 2\pi x$$

It is second order ordinary differential equation. Using the method of undetermined coefficients to solve it. Thus its particular solution is

$$F(x, \mu^\alpha, \beta) = \frac{3\mu^\beta \sin 2\pi x}{\mu^\alpha + 4\pi^2},$$

Taking inverse Hunaiber transform, we get

$$f(x, t) = 3 \sin 2\pi x e^{-4\pi^2 t}.$$

IV. CONCLUSION

There are a lot of the integral transforms of exponential type kernels, the Hunaiber transform is new and very powerful among them and there are many problems in applied sciences and engineering can be solved by Hunaiber transform. Fundamental Properties of Hunaiber transform is proved. An application Hunaiber transform to the solution of partial differential equations has been demonstrated.

REFERENCES

1. N. S. Abhale and S. S. Pawar, Fundamental Properties of Sadik Transform and its Applications, Journal of Applied Science and Computations, 6 (3) (2019) 995-999.
2. S. Aggarwal, R. Chauhan and N. Sharma, A New Application of Mahgoub Transform for Solving

- Linear Volterra Integral Equations, Asian Resonance, 7(2) (2018) 46-48.
3. T. M. Elzaki and S. M. Ezaki, Application of New Transform "Elzaki Transform" to Partial Differential Equations, Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, 7(1) (2011) 65–70.
 4. T. M. Elzaki and S. M. Ezaki, New Integral Transform "Tarig Transform" and System of Integro-Differential Equations, Elixir Appl. Math., 93(2016) 39758-39761.
 5. M. Hunaiber, The New Integral Transform "Hunaiber Transform", International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review, 4 (4) (2022) 2617-2619.
 6. A. Kılıçman and Hassan Eltayeb, A Note on Integral Transforms and Partial Differential Equations, Applied Mathematical Sciences, 4(3) (2010) 109-118.
 7. S. Maitama and W. Zhao, New Integral Transform: Shehu Transform A Generalization of Sumudu and Laplace Transform for Solving Differential Equations, International Journal of Analysis and Applications, 17(2)(2019) 167-190.
 8. M. M. Mahgoub, The New Integral Transform "Mahgoub Transform", Advances in Theoretical and Applied Mathematics, 11(4) (2016) 391-398.
 9. D. P. Patil, Aboodh and Mahgoub Transform in Boundary Value Problems of System of Ordinary Differential Equations, International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology, 6 (1) (2021) 67-75.
 10. S. S. Pawar and N. S. Abhale, Applications of Sadik Transform for solving Bessel's Function and linear Volterra Integral Equation of Convolution type, Cikitusi Journal for Multidisciplinary Research, 6 (3) (2019) 85-91.
 11. S. S. Redhwan, S. L. Shaikh and M. S. Abdo, Some Properties of Sadik Transform and Its Applications of Fractional-Order Dynamical Systems in Control Theory, Advances in the Theory of Nonlinear Analysis and its Applications, 4 (2020) (1) 51–66.
 12. S. Sabarinathan, D. Muralidharan and A. P. Selvan, Application of Mahgoub Integral Transform to Bessel's Differential Equations, Communications in Mathematics and Applications, 12 (4) (2021) 919–930.
 13. A. K. Sedeeg and Z. I. Mahamoud, The Use of Kamal Transform for Solving Partial Differential Equations, Advances in Theoretical and Applied Mathematics, 12 (1) (2017) 7-13.
 14. S. L. Shaikh, Some Applications of The New Integral Transform For Partial Differential Equations, Mathematical Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences, 7(1) (2018) 45–49.
 15. S. L. Shaikh, Introducing a New Integral Transform: Sadik Transform, American International Journal of Research in Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics, 22 (1) (2018) 100-102.